

Heavy Metal Toxicity and Associated Health Risks in Animal and Fishes

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Abstract: *The marine ecosystem is severely contaminated with heavy metals. Some of these are referred to be essential heavy metals because they have vital biological roles for aquatic creatures. Heavy metal levels that are hazardous can result from mining, industry, and agriculture. This will result in alterations to the physicochemical properties of the aquatic environment as well as contamination of the water body. Fish are negatively impacted by this pollution, which is harmful to them and may have negative impacts on human health. The most prevalent heavy metals that are regarded as systemic toxicants and have an impact on human health are arsenic, chromium, lead, and mercury. Pb, Hg, Cd, Cr, Cu, Zn, Mn, Ni, Ag, and more are the main heavy metals. The heavy metals—As, Cd, Pb, and Hg—are thought to be the most hazardous to people, pets, fish, and the environment. Heavy metal concentrations that are too high are harmful. Because they bioaccumulate in organisms, have harmful effects on the biota, and may even cause death in most living things, they disrupt ecosystems. All heavy metals cause mutagenesis and metabolic disruption in living things, despite the fact that some of them are vital micronutrients. For the aforementioned reasons, this review was written to add to the understanding of the toxic mechanism, environmental function, and toxic consequences of heavy metals on fish and mammals.*

Keywords: Heavy metals; Toxicity; Health; Mechanism; Plasma membrane; Mammals

Introduction: Surpassing all other animal husbandry businesses worldwide in recent years, the aquaculture sector has grown at a far quicker pace. About 6% of all protein consumed by humans comes from aquaculture, which accounts for roughly 17% of animal protein [1]. It offers a rich amount of animal protein with minimal saturated fat and omega-3 fatty acids, along with vitamin B [2-4]. However, eating fish may put human health at risk from a variety of contaminants, the most significant and prevalent of which are heavy metals. The earth's crust naturally contains heavy metals, which are metallic chemical elements with a high potential for toxicity at low concentrations. These elements are also thought to be a naturally occurring trace element in the aquatic environment, with a maximum allowable concentration (Table-1) that has been exceeded because of agricultural and industrial practices [5-7]. Numerous factors contribute to water pollution, such as paint on ships, PVC stabilizers, and agricultural practices using pesticides and fungicides, which raise the risk to fish and people as well as other invertebrates and vertebrates [8, 9].

Fish are affected by the accumulation of heavy metals in their bodies, which occurs in the aquatic environment. Compared to marine fish, freshwater fish are more susceptible to heavy metal exposure. This is because, in contrast to marine fish, which often lose water and acquire salt, freshwater fish tend to gain water and lose salt [10]. Through ingestion, gills and skin (Ion exchange), or adsorption by fish tissues, heavy metals can enter the body of a fish [11]. Numerous variables, such as water solubility, eating habits, ecology, and fish physiology—including species, age, size, reproductive status, fish health, bioavailability, and various habitats—affect the accumulation of metals in different areas of the body [12].

These days, pollution is a major concern that poses risks to both the environment and the world's expanding population. The rapid industrialization and urbanization of society has resulted in a greater release of radioactive elements, heavy metals, and other organic and inorganic contaminants into the environment. Therefore, the primary source of metal contamination for aquatic creatures is industrial waste. According to some reports, the main environmental contaminants are heavy metals. Because heavy metals are abundant in mineral organic compounds and cannot be removed from aquatic systems by natural means like organic contaminants, they are significant pollutants for fish. The aquatic system is severely harmed by the metal pollutants that are mixed in through the smelting process, effluents, sewage, and leaching of waste. The aquatic environment now contains more toxins due to the tanning business. Because of their hormone disrupting properties, the tannery waste waters still pose a threat to aquatic life. Tanners utilize a lot of chemicals in their operation, which releases hazardous elements into the waterways. The result is a degradation of the agricultural fields as well. The threats to many creatures' health have escalated due to the uncontrolled leakage of tannery effluents [13].

The presence of toxic algae can lead to nutrient contamination, such as nitrogen and phosphates, which can cause aquatic species to die. Chemical pollution can lead to a decrease in tadpole quantity and biodiversity in frog populations. Chemical contamination, or oil pollution, can have a detrimental effect on marine creature growth. It impairs reproduction and makes one more susceptible to illness. In addition, it may irritate the gastrointestinal tract and harm the kidneys, liver, and brain system. The excessive concentration of sodium chloride (NaCl) in waterways may potentially be the cause of animal fatalities in aquatic environments. Byproducts from a variety of industries, including manufacturing, farming, city septic systems, construction, automobile garages, labs, and hospitals, are extremely hazardous. These leftovers, which might be liquid, solid, or sludge-like, may contain radiation, heavy metals, chemicals, pathogens, or other hazardous substances. Toxins can also be produced by objects like batteries, outdated computer hardware, and residual paint or pesticide. These wastes are poisonous to people, animals, and plants whether they are buried in the ground, present in stream runoff, groundwater for drinking, or in flooding. When fish are consumed by humans or other animals, hazardous elements like mercury can build up in the aquatic system and become harmful to them. According to the USA's "Environmental Protection Agency" (EPA), hazardous items must be handled carefully and disposed of appropriately. The heavy metals are more frequently used with fertilizers. However, certain plants absorb the hazardous

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quantities of these metals, which are then ingested by humans and have a very negative impact on offspring [14].

Table 1. Heavy metal permissible concentrations [15]

Heavy metal	Allowed concentration (PPM)
Arsenic	0.01
Lead	0.015
Aluminum	0.2
Mercury	0.002
Copper	1.4
Chromium	0.05

Heavy Metals' Risks to the Environment and Health: When heavy metals undergo absorption, they accumulate in living things and are not as quickly digested or eliminated as they are. Heavy metals can find their way into water supplies through consumer and industrial waste, or even by acidic rain that dissolves soils and releases heavy metals into rivers, lakes, streams, and groundwater. According to reports, Pb, Hg, and Cd are the three most common environmental heavy metal pollutants [7, 16]. The term "bioaccumulation" refers to the gradual rise in a chemical or toxin's concentration within a biological organism relative to that of the environment. It is significant to note that the majority of zoos that were formerly found on the outskirts of towns and cities are now encircled by human activity, including industry and transportation. All of these activities have the potential to pollute heavy metals, which might have a negative impact on the health and welfare of the wild animals kept in these protected regions.³ The hazards to the environment and human health posed by different heavy metal pollution are listed below [17].

Mechanism of heavy metal toxicity: The metallic elements known as heavy metals, which include mercury, arsenic, aluminum, lead, and chromium, can cause toxicity in humans and other vertebrates even at low concentrations. They do this by interfering with cellular organelles such as mitochondrial lysosomes, cell membranes, and endoplasmic reticulum, which disrupts metabolism, tissue repair, and cell and organ detoxification [18]. They can also attack and combine with DNA molecules and cause cell cycle modulation, carcinogenesis, and apoptosis [19]. The main harmful mechanism that arises from the unbalanced control of the antioxidant system and the generation of free radicals (ROS) as a result of cell membrane disruptions is oxidative stress [20]. Aluminum may enter natural waters via water treatment facilities, coal strip mining activities, industrial wastes and acid rainfall. Metal toxicity is magnified in the aquatic environment, accompanied by high organic matter content with low water pH [21]. The majority of biological and physical functions are hampered by aluminum. The plasma membrane induces respiratory stress, coagulation of mucus on the gill, lamellar fusion, and abnormalities in osmoregulation and ionic balance. In addition to endocrine

disturbance, fish exposed to Al experience pathological alterations in the cardiovascular, respiratory, ion-regulatory, hemoglobin concentration, and growth [22].

Figure 1. Mechanism of heavy metal toxicity such as lead (Pb), silver (Ag), and cadmium (Cd) can directly penetrate through the plasma membrane

Arsenic reaches the aquatic environment through the industrial effluents as smelting operations and electric generators effusions and agricultural run-off, whereas the arsenic intake is through gills or contaminated feeds [23]. Suhendrayatna et al., (2002b) reported the LC50 for *Oryzias Latipes* were 14.6 and 30.3 mg /l, acute exposure to arsenic causes sudden fish death because of increase mucous secretion, defect in gill epithelium and suffocation. In contrast, in chronic exposure, it may accumulate in different tissue and cause several pathological changes [24]. Arsenic also accumulates in the retina and interferes with the immune system, leading to depletion of both B and T lymphocytes from lymphatic organs with variant toxicity according to the time of exposure to Arsenic [25].

Among all the heavy metals, lead is the most dangerous. Although lead is a naturally occurring element in the environment, human activity has significantly increased its concentration. Fish species have acute lethal concentrations between 10 and 100 mg/l. Lead's bioavailability is influenced by the physical and chemical characteristics of water, including its pH, alkalinity, hardness, and naturally occurring organic matter concentration [26, 27]. While the gills are the primary site of lead precipitation in fish, even though lead enters fish bodies through diet, the main pathological effects of chronic lead toxicity in *Clarisas garipepinus* are epithelial damage,

desquamation, and aneurism. One response is thought to be a physiological compensatory mechanism [28]. Chromium enters the body by the digestive tract or gills, just like other heavy metals, however it is known to accumulate less quickly than other metals. According to Ackermann (2008), the histological findings in the gills, kidneys, liver, and gonads of *Oreochromis massambicus* subjected to sublethal concentrations of Cr+6 are mostly due to the suppression of essential metabolic and physiologic processes [29].

Accumulation of metal ion and action: Any chemical that has the potential to generate negative or harmful consequences when taken into the body is considered poisonous. It has been reported that a number of metals and their derivatives are poisonous to animals. The most hazardous heavy metals have reportedly been identified as As, Cu, Pb, Hg, and Cd. It's thought that a lot of hazardous metals cause harm to animals by interfering with their enzyme systems. Many of them compete with other chemicals required for cell maintenance and survival because they attach to certain enzymes and proteins required for cellular function. As a result, the toxins may also cause a lack of certain minerals [30]. Aquaculture is also associated with severe toxicity and the bioaccumulation of many heavy metal pollutants. These kinds of aquacultures will cause fish quality to decline, which will be bad for the population that consumes fish. In lipids, methyl mercury is thousands of times more soluble than in water. The brain, central nervous system, and muscular tissues contain the majority of this methyl mercury (Hg). Fish concentrations of mercury can exceed 10,000 to 100,000 times the initial levels in the nearby waterways.

For saltwater fish, the average Hg and Se levels ranged from 0.35 to 70.02 ppm and 0.37 to 70.01 ppm, respectively. Bluefish contain levels of mercury that are more than enough to poison fish-eating animals and birds. Average values of more than 0.3 ppm have been found for fish larger than 50 cm fork length. This implies that eating such tainted seafood is not advised for children, pregnant women, or other susceptible people. It implies that the sole major source of methyl mercury for humans comes from fish intake. High, prolonged exposure to methyl mercury and other organic contaminants might have a greater negative impact on the population that depends on eating fish on a regular basis. Similarly, upscale fish eaters are also extremely [31]. After that, the heavy metals poison the enzyme system, increase the generation of "free radicals," and compete with necessary components to produce metallo-enzyme complexes that compete with the absorption of minerals from food [32]. In general, all heavy metals are harmful to cells. They compete with the nutritional minerals and make them inaccessible to the body, which might result in illness.

Conclusion: The heavy metals—As, Cd, Pb, and Hg—are the most harmful to fish, animals, humans, and the environment. Excessive concentrations of heavy metals are extremely hazardous. All heavy metals show their harmful effects through metabolic disruption and mutagenesis, even though certain heavy metals are necessary for plants, animals, and a number of other creatures. All of the Pb and Hg are extremely harmful. Fish are not an exception, and heavy metal pollution in them can have detrimental consequences and cause major issues. Different organs may be poisoned by heavy metals. Drainage, atmospheric pressure, soil

erosion, and other human activities are some of the ways they can get into the water. As environmental concentrations of heavy metals rise, these substances enter the biogeochemical cycle and cause toxicity in fish and other species.

Competing interest: None.

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